

LITERACY, SENSITIVITY AND OPPORTUNITIES IN DEVELOPING ENVIRONMENTALLY RESPONSIVE BEHAVIOR AMONG GRADE 7 LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

The study sought to describe the environmental literacy and environmentally responsible behavior of Grade 7 students of Sto. Tomas Integrated High School. Furthermore, it attempted to know if there is a significant relationship between environmentally responsible behavior and environmental literacy as to context, competencies, knowledge and disposition. Using a descriptive correlation design, the study involved 150 Grade 7 students of Sto. Tomas Integrated High School who were randomly selected. The study was administered during the third quarter of the school year 2020-2021. The student-respondents were asked to answer survey questionnaire to determine the level of the Environmental Literacy and the extent of practice of Environmentally Responsible Behavior. Survey questionnaires were validated by the panel of examiners and group of teachers. Results revealed that there was a significant relationship between environmentally responsible behavior and environmental literacy as to context, competency and disposition while no significant relationship was obtained between environmentally responsible behavior and environmental literacy as to knowledge.

Keywords: environmental literacy, environmentally responsible behavior